

ESSENTIAL OIL FROM THE LEAVES OF BEL (*AEGLE MARMELOS*)

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Essential oil is extracted from the leaves of *Aegle marmelos*. Its chief component is found to be α -*d*-phellandrene which forms about 56% of the oil.

The tree of *Aegle marmelos*, popularly known in vernacular as Bêl and in Sanskrit as 'Bilwa' is indigenous to India and belongs to the family of Rutaceae.

The earliest reference to the essential oil extracted from the leaves of the plant is found in Gildmeister and Hoffmann's treatise (The Ethereal Oils, Vol. III, p. 648). The relevant part of the reference is quoted below :—

"According to a communication by Ritsemma (J aal dep. landb. in NedIndic Batavia, 1908, p.52) the leaves yielded upon distillation about 0.6% of an oil with a light yellow colour, d_{25}° , 0.856; $[\alpha]_{D}^{20}$, 10.71. Distillation resulted in the following fractions :

I (up to 100°), 5g. II (100° to 130°), 5.1g., III (130° to 160°). 1g. Residue, 1.5 g.

Fraction II contained limonene which was characterised by its boiling point (175°) and its tetrabromide (m.p. 104°). Aldehydes could not be detected. On prolonged standing the oil becomes viscid."

Dikshit and Dutta (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 759) extracted dried leaves of the plant with various solvents and obtained tannin, reducing sugars, etc. They make no reference about the occurrence of the terpenes or any odoriferous component which obviously must have been lost during the drying of leaves. With a view therefore to ascertaining the chemical composition of the oil of Indian source we have extracted the oil from fresh leaves of Bêl the composition of which (Table I) differs widely from that of the oil referred to by Gildmeister and Hoffmann (*loc. cit.*).

The leaves on steam-distillation gave an oil in 0.6% yield. It was noticed that the yield of the oil from young leaves was somewhat greater than from the mature leaves. The oil gave the following properties.

TABLE I

I. d_{26}°	..	..	..	0.8476	IV. Acid value	..	..	..	20
II. n_D^{31}	..	..	..	1.4750	V. Sapon. value				16.1
III. $[\alpha]_D^{20}$	..	..	..	52.1	VI. Citral content of oil*				3.76%

* By the method of thiosemicarbazide of Radcliffe and Swann (*Perf. & Ess. Oil Rec.*, 1928, 10, 47)

On careful fractionation of the oil under reduced pressure three fractions were collected whose properties and % yield are shown in Table II. Fraction I constituting about 56% of the oil is presumed to be a single substance, as on repeated distillations under atmospheric pressure it boiled within a narrow range of 173° to 175°. Quantitative analysis, however, showed that this fraction consisted mostly of a terpene mixed with a small proportion of an oxygen containing compound. The terpene formed a nitrosite (m.p. 105°). From the boiling point of the terpene and the melting point of its nitrosite, as also from other properties shown in Table III, the terpene has been identified as α -*d*-phellandrene.

The oxygen containing compound intimately mixed with the terpene gave reactions of cineol. Thus fraction I, when shaken with syrupy phosphoric acid, gave a semisolid mass on cooling characteristic of cineol. Further, when this fraction was warmed with a little iodol (tetrahydropyrrole, C_4H_7NH) the additive compound of cineol and iodol separated as a yellowish crystalline mass (cf. Bertram and Walbaum, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1897, 235, 178). The quantity of iodol, however, was insufficient for further purification by crystallisation. These products of cineol were compared by us with the corresponding products which we prepared from pure cineol from authentic specimen of eucalyptus oil.

The separation of α -*d*-phellandrene from cineol in fraction I was effected by washing fraction with 50% aqueous resorcinol in which the cineol dissolved (in the form of its product with resorcinol) (*Sch. Ber.*, 1907, 5, 32). The phellandrene which remained dissolved gave on purification and analysis results agreeing with the composition $C_{10}H_{16}$. Cineol separated from resorcinol solution on addition of alkali and boiled at 176° .

The nitrosite of phellandrene prepared by us melted at 105° , but on recrystallisation its melting point rose to 113° . Read and Storey (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 2770) prepared nitrosite of phellandrene which they obtained from piperitol by dehydration. The authors mention that the melting point of their nitrosite rose after crystallisation from 105° to 110° and finally to 113° .

We have noted like the previous observers that the optical rotation of the nitrosite of phellandrene is opposite in direction to the rotation of the phellandrene itself. Thus α -*d*-phellandrene forms a *laevo*-rotatory nitrosite (Wallach and Beschke, *Annalen*, 1904, 336, 40) and α -*l*-phellandrene forms a *dextro*-rotatory nitrosite (Read, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1597). The specific rotation of the nitrosite of α -*d*-phellandrene prepared by us was -47° and it does not agree with the value given by Wallach, which is -138° . Although we cannot explain the discrepancy at this stage, it must be pointed out that the phellandrenes as well as their nitrosites are unstable. Different rotations have been recorded for phellandrenes obtained from different sources (Table III). The nitrosites of phellandrenes in solution exhibit mutarotation. Read (*loc. cit.*) records that the rotation of α -nitrosite of α -*l*-phellandrene changes from $+130^\circ$ in 48 minutes and to -45.8° in 115 hours. We observed that the rotation of the α -nitrosite of α -*d*-phellandrene prepared by us changed from -47° to $+42.6^\circ$ in 3 days.

Fraction II boiling between 104° and $130^\circ/130$ mm. was redistilled at atmospheric pressure when most of it passed between 205° and 208° . It reduced Fehling's solution and gave the general reactions of an aldehyde. The bisulphite compound of the aldehyde was prepared by the method of Tiemann (*Ber.*, 1898, 31, 3307) and the semicarbazone, prepared directly from the aldehyde, melted at 84° . From its boiling point and the melting point of its semicarbazone the aldehyde was identified as citronellal. Fraction III and the two derivatives (the bisulphite and the semicarbazone) were compared by us with the corresponding derivatives of citronellal (prepared from Java citronella oil) and its two derivatives.

Fraction III began to distil above 210° at atmospheric pressure, but it soon began to polymerise due to polymerisation. This also gave reactions of an aldehyde. Its bisulphite compound was prepared by Tiemann's method and directly from the aldehyde the semicarbazone was prepared in presence of free acetic acid (distinction from the method for preparing citronellal semicarbazone). On crystallisation the semicarbazone melted at 163° . From the boiling range of the aldehyde and the formation of its semicarbazone in presence of free acetic acid, and the melting point of the semicarbazone, the aldehyde was identified as citral. The aldehyde and its derivatives were compared by us with pure citral (obtained by us from pure lemon grass oil from Holland) and its derivatives.

EXPERIMENTAL

Isolation of the Essential Oil.—The essential oil was obtained by steam-distillation of the leaves from a copper still fitted with a spiral copper condenser. The oil separated from the aqueous distillate as a light yellow layer floating over water. It was carefully separated from water which was returned to the still for next distillation. The oil, dried over calcium chloride, gave properties, shown in Table I.

Fractionation of the Oil.—The oil (80 c.c.) was fractionally distilled at 130 mm. pressure. Three fractions were collected; the boiling ranges, percentage yields and properties of the fractions are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

No.	B. p. (130 mm.)	Vol.	Yield.	B. p. at atmospheric pressure.	Properties. M.p. of their derivatives
I	80°—104°	45 c.c.	56%	173°—174°	Nitrosite, 105°
II	104°—130°	17	21	205°—208°	Semicarbazone, 84°
III	130°—160°	7	9	Above 210°	Semicarbazone, 164°

Isolation of Pure α -d-Phellandrene from Fraction I.—This fraction was distilled at atmospheric pressure when 40 c.c. were collected between 173° and 174°. The distillate was shaken with 50% aqueous resorcinol which dissolved cineol. The phellandrene remaining undissolved was repeatedly washed with water till free from resorcinol; it was dried and distilled from a flask with a fractionating column. The portion boiling at 174° was analysed. (Found: C, 88.0; H, 11.7. $C_{10}H_{16}$ requires C, 88.2; H, 11.8 per cent).

Isolation of Cineol.—From the aqueous resorcinol solution the cineol was liberated by adding alkali, shaking vigorously and then extracting with ether. On drying and removing the solvent the residual liquid boiled at 176°.

The Nitrosite.—To a solution of fraction I (10 c.c.) in petroleum ether (20 c.c.) was added an aqueous solution of sodium nitrite (10g. in 15 c.c.). After cooling well by freezing mixture glacial acetic acid (10 g.) was gradually added when the nitrosite began to separate as a white crystalline mass which was filtered, washed with water and finally with methyl alcohol. The crude dry nitrosite was purified by dissolving in chloroform and precipitating by the addition of methyl alcohol. It melted at 105°. By repeating the above process m.p. rose to 114°.

The nitrosite dissolves freely in chloroform and shows optical rotation, $[\alpha]_D = -47$ in that solvent. A comparison between the properties of the phellandrene obtained from the essential oil with those of this terpene described in literature is made in Table III.

TABLE III

No.	Properties.	Fraction I.	α -d-Phellandrene
I.	B.p.	173° to 174°	172° (Pesci, <i>Ber.</i> , 1886, 19, 874); 175° to 170° (obtained from ginger grass oil, Walbaum and Huthig, <i>J. prakt. Chem.</i> , 1905, ii, 71, 480).
II.	n	1.477 (at 31°)	1.488 at 19°.
III.	$[\alpha]_D$	+49.1°	+44.4° (Walbaum & Huthig <i>loc. cit.</i>) +17.64° (Pesci, <i>loc. cit.</i>) 60.21° (Gildmeister and Stephens, <i>Arch. Pharm.</i> , 1897, 235, 591.)
IV.	M.p. of nitrosite	105°	105° (Read & Storey <i>J. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1930, 2770.)

The α -*d*-phellandrene was prepared by Read and Storey (*loc. cit.*) by dehydration of *d*-piperitol which was shown by Simonsen (*Indian Forest Records*, 1924, Part VIII, p. 10) to occur in the essential oil of a species of *Andropogon* growing in United Provinces.

Sodium Bisulphite Compound and Semicarbazone of Citronellal.—Fraction II, which when distilled at atmospheric pressure, boiled mostly between 205° and 208°. A cold saturated solution of sodium sulphite was added to 2 c.c. of this fraction kept cool by ice. On adding gradually glacial acetic acid (equivalent amount) and vigorous shaking crystals of the bisulphite compound began to separate. These were filtered off and freed from the adhering oil by pressing between filter papers and drying on a porous plate. The crystals were dissolved in excess of water and to the clear solution was added a strong solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride and sodium acetate. On cooling by freezing mixture and vigorous shaking the semicarbazone separated which was filtered off, dried and recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 84° (citronellal semicarbazone, m.p. 86°.)

Sodium Bisulphite Compound and Semicarbazone of Citral.—The sodium bisulphite compound was prepared from fraction III in the manner described above. To the clear solution of this in water a solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride and sodium acetate together with free acetic acid were added. On cooling and shaking the mixture the citral semicarbazone separated. This on recrystallisation melted at 163° (semicarbazone from an authentic specimen of citral melted at 164°).